

INFLUENCE OF CREEP LOAD ON AGING AND FRACTURE MECHANIC BEHAVIOUR OF SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED PEEK

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Mechanical tests

Setup for static tests

Static tests are unavoidable for a full long time material behaviour characterisation of polymers. Even for cyclic loads, the static load behaviour is (with theoretically zero amplitude at a certain load level) the limitation. The same principle can be used for fracture mechanic tests. Since short fibre reinforced polymers are investigated, also the fibre orientation needed to be considered. The results show a similar effect of the fibre orientation on the static strength for a certain time to failure.

Fracture mechanics

The time to failure is very sensitive to changes in the stress intensity factor

Specimen shape and calculation according to ASTM E 647-11

$$K = [P / (B \cdot \sqrt{W})] \cdot F$$

Static tests

IR-Measurements

ATR FT-IR microscopy for the IR measurements

Specimen with points for the IR measurements

There is a very low influence of the stress intensity factor on the IR spectrum on the crack for the investigated polymer and specimen due to the inert properties.

Positions and FTIR spectrum of crack near points (longitudinal)

Positions and FTIR spectrum of crack near points (transverse)

Acknowledgement

This research forms part of the research programme of DPI, project # 851 Technology Area: D02 Performance Polymers 2.0

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